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Computational screening of potential ulcer inhibitors from *Moringa oleifera* Lam. leaves

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ABSTRACT

The genus *Moringa* Adans. comprises 13 species, of which *Moringa oleifera* Lam. native to India and cultivated across the world. *Moringa* is a well valued plant that is cultivated in tropical environments. It is well known for its nutritional values and ability to attack many diseases. This study explores the ulcer inhibiting ability of *Moringa oleifera* via in-silico method. The chemical contents of *Moringa oleifera* were revealed though GC-MS experiment. The molecules found in the plant were subjected to ulcer screening using molecular docking method. The molecular docking result showed that Kaempferol (-6.6 kcal mol⁻¹, -10.7 kcal mol⁻¹) and Catechin (-6.6 kcal mol⁻¹, -10.5 kcal mol⁻¹) gave very good docking scores in 2 ulcer proteins, Helicobacter pylori adhesin HopQ type I (PBD 6gbg) and Protein HP1028 from the human pathogen Helicobacter pylori lipocalin family (PDB 4inn), the results even surpassed the control drug Omeprazole which gave binding scores of (-6.6 kcal mol⁻¹, -9.1 kcal mol⁻¹) in the two proteins respectively. Absorption, distribution, metabolism elimination and toxicity (ADMET) screening were undertaken on omeprazole, Kaempferol and Catechin to ascertain their drug properties. The result showed that the compounds are good drug lead candidates for the inhibition of ulcer wounds in human. None of the compounds violated the Lipinski's rule of five. To define the reactivities of the compounds towards the proteins, density functional theory calculations were performed, the results showed very values of quantum chemical parameters in all the compounds indicating that the transfer of electrons between them and the proteins would be easy and this aids reactivity and function ability of chemical compounds as drugs.

Keywords: *Moringa oleifera*, docking, drugs, omeprazole, Kaempferol

1. INTRODUCTION

Ulcer is a disease that is characterized by the removal of the surface of the digestive system by the gastric juice or digestive enzymes found in the digestive tract [1-3]. Ulcer affects various locations in the digestive system. Depending on the location, we have peptic (gastric and duodenal), mouth, esophageal, arterial, genital, venous as well as diabetic foot ulcers. Peptic ulcer is the most common type of ulcer that affect the global population and if not checked can lead to increased global mortality [4-6]. Despite available treatment options, the disease still torments majority of the African populace, therefore sustainable strategies need to be explored including the search for edible plant materials that will impact less side effect on the user.

Medicinal plants are those that some or all their parts are used for therapeutic applications or that may be used as a precursor for chemo-pharmaceutical semi-synthesis [7]. Compounds from medicinal plants have proven effective in the management of several diseases including ulcer sores (8). *Moringa oleifera* is one plant that has been used as medicine for the treatment of various diseases, almost all its parts are useful, the leaves, stem and roots [9, 10]. In traditional herbal medicine the plant is very effective for the treatment of ulcers, wounds, liver diseases, pain, heart disease, inflammation and cancer [11]. The leaves are rich in beta-carotene, potassium, iron, phosphorus, calcium and vitamin C [12, 13].

Molecular docking is a very important tool used in drug discovery to predict the binding affinities when small molecules (ligands) bind to receptors proteins [14]. It anticipates the most favorable orientation of the small molecule (ligand) against protein (receptor) with the aim of forming a stable complex. The most favoured orientation is used in predicting the binding strength or binding affinity between the ligand and protein by using scoring functions. Molecular docking performs specific roles for determining the important pharmacological activity of new or existing drug substances [15]. The most important role of docking is to enhance an optimized conformation and to simulate the molecular identification process thereby reducing the free energy of the system [16, 17].

The present work screens compounds from *Moringa oleifera* for their ulcer inhibiting properties using computational method.

2. METHODOLOGY

2. 1. Preparation of plant material

The *Moringa oleifera* leaves used in this project were harvested from a local garden in Owerri North local government of Imo state, Nigeria. Authenticated by Prof M. Mbagwu of the plant science and Biotechnology Department of Imo State University, Owerri. The leaves were dried to a low moisture content, ground to powdered form and dipped in Chloroform to extract the phytochemicals, the content was left unstirred for 24-h after which filtration was done using whatman grade 1 cellulose filter paper. The residue was discarded while the filtrate was concentrated and sent for GC-MS analysis.

2. 2. Gas chromatography mass spectrophotometry experiment

Gc-ms analysis was conducted on the previously prepared plant material with the aid of Agilent GC MS instrument and parameter 0 °C - 325 °C (350 °C): 30 m × 250 µm × 0.25 µm

with model number 19091S-433UI USA [18] using initial temperature of 50 °C and pressure of 7.3614 psi and final temperature and pressure of 325 °C and 0 psi respectively. The carrier gas was helium and the flow rate was left at 0.97414 mL/min,

2. 3. Preparation of ligands

The phytochemicals extracted from the plant material were used as ligands for the molecular docking analysis. Their 3-dimentional structures were downloaded from pubchem database [19] and saved as 3-dimensional structure data files (SDF).

2. 4. Protein Preparation

X-Ray crystallography structures of two ulcer proteins: Helicobacter pylori adhesin HopQ type I (PBD 6gbg) [20] and Protein HP1028 from the human pathogen Helicobacter pylori belongs to the lipocalin family (PDB 4inn) [21] were downloaded from protein databank (PDB) database. the proteins were prepared in discovery studio where the co-crystallized water molecules, ligand chain and other protein chains were removed.

2. 5. Molecular Docking Interaction

Each prepared protein was uploaded in the pyrX visual screening software [22] and made the macromolecule for the docking interaction. The ligands were minimized and converted to autodock ligands (pdbqt) [23]. Molecular docking between the protein and ligands were performed in the Autodock vina imbibed the pyrX virtual screening software.

2. 6. Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Elimination (ADMET) Screening

Three compounds with low docking scores were selected and screened for Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Elimination properties using admetSAR 2.0: web-software for prediction and optimization of chemical ADMET properties [24].

2. 7. Density Functional Theory calculation (DFT)

Density Functional Theory calculations were undertaken on the compounds to ascertain the relationship between their structures and reactivities. The DFT calculations were performed in the material studio 7.0 modeling/simulation software by acceryl. Company Inc with DMol [25].

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3. 1. Gas chromatography mass spectrophotometry Result

Gas chromatography-mass spectrophotometry experiment was performed on the crude extract to provide insight into the chemical composition of the plant. Phytochemicals obtained from the GC-MS analysis are presented in Table 1, Figure 1 shows the chromatogram and Figure 2 show the mass spectrum of Kaempferol one of the identified compounds. Some prominent components of the GC-MS result with composition greater than 4.00% are cis-Vaccenic acid (12.04 %), trans-13-Octadecenoic acid (4.71 %) Ferulic (4.67 %) Catechin (4.67

%) and Kaempferol (4.64 %). These compounds have been previously used in molecular docking for disease control [26-28].

mol⁻¹) gave very low binding affinities in 6gbg and 4inn proteins respectively showing that they most effectively inhibited the diseases even surpassing the control drug which gave (-6.6 Kcal mol⁻¹, -9.1 Kcal mol⁻¹). Interestingly Kaempferol and catechin were in high concentrations in the plant extract 4.64% and 4.67 % respectively suggesting that these two compounds participated actively in the ulcer inhibition. Comprehensive visualized representation of the interactions between the ulcer proteins and the ligands are presented in Figure 3.

Abundance

Figure 2. Mass spectrum of kaempferol.

Omeprazole, the control drug interacted with the active site of 6gbg via Vander Waals forces, conventional hydrogen bonding, carbon hydrogen bond, alkyl and pi-alkyl bonds, the interaction in 4inn protein was via Waals forces, conventional hydrogen bonding, pi-donor hydrogen bond, pi-sigma, pi-sulfur, pi-pi T-shaped, alky and pi-alkyl. Kaempferol interacted with 6gbg protein through Vander Waals forces, conventional hydrogen bonding, pi-pi stacked,

pi-alkyl while interacting with 4inn via Van der Waals, conventional hydrogen bond, carbon hydrogen bond, unfavorable donor-donor, pi-sigma, pi-pi stacked, pi-pi T-shaped and pi-alkyl. Catechin interacted with the 6gbg protein via Van der Waals, conventional hydrogen bond, pi-sulfur, pi-pi T-shaped and pi-alkyl and with the 4inn protein via Van der Waals, conventional hydrogen bond, unfavorable donor-donor, pi-donor hydrogen bond, pi-sigma, pi-pi T-shaped.

Table 1. Compounds identified from the GC-MS experiment, pubchem cid, binding scores.

Serial No.	Area %	Compound	Pubchem cid	Binding energy (Kcal/mol) 6gbg	Binding energy (Kcal/mol) 4inn
1.	Control drug	Omeprazole	4594	-6.6	-9.1
2.	0.65	Cyclodecene	5365612	-4.7	-6.7
3	0.76	Undecane	14257	-4.4	-5.7
4.	0.53	Dodecane	8182	-3.8	-6.1
5.	0.19	Tridecane	12388	-4.3	-6.1
6.	2.51	9-Eicosene, (E)-	5365037	-4.4	-7.1
7	1.27	Cyclotetradecane	67524	-5.6	-9.1
8	1.45	Tetradecane	12389	-3.6	-6.3
9	0.29	cis-1,4-Cyclohexanediamine, N-methyl	21938416	-4.7	-5.7
10.	1.95	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	7311	-5.7	-5.8
11	0.34	Undecanoic acid, 10-methyl-, methyl ester	554144	-4.8	-6.6
12	2.60	Dodecanoic acid	3893	-4.9	-6.5
13	0.39	9-Octadecene, (E)-	5364599	-4.6	-7.0
14	0.44	Hexadecane	11006	-4.0	-6.3
15	0.95	1-Dodecene	8183	-3.3	-5.8
16	0.67	Tetradecanoic acid	11005	-4.9	-6.0
17	0.27	1-Octadecanesulphonyl chloride	66281	-4.1	-7.3
18	2.37	n-Hexadecanoic acid	985	-5.0	-7.1
19	4.68	Ferulic	445858	-6.8	-7.1
20	0.16	Methoxyacetic acid, 2-tetradecyl ester	545729	-3.9	-7.0

21	0.11	Cyclohexane, 1,1'-(1,4-butanediyl) bis	22546	-6.2	-8.1
22	0.18	9-Octadecenoic acid, (E)-	637517	-5.1	-7.3
23	0.12	Methyl stearate	8201	-4.6	-6.7
24	5.09	trans-13-Octadecenoic acid	6161490	-4.3	-7.1
25	12.04	cis-Vaccenic acid	5282761	-4.9	-7.2
26	2.53	Limonene	7095	-6.0	-8.0
27	0.70	Cyclohexane, 1-(1,5-dimethylhexyl)-4-(4-methylpentyl)-	41687	-5.5	-8.4
28.	3.69	1-Docosene	74138	-3.4	-7.1
29.	0.92	1-Octadecanesulphonyl chloride	66281	-4.3	-6.4
30	1.90	1-Eicosene	18936	-4.2	-6.9
31	1.28	Cyclohexadecane, 1,2-diethyl-	536940	-6.7	-6.9
32	0.64	Cycloeicosane	520444	-6.4	-6.7
33	0.41	2-Methyl-Z,Z-3,13-octadecadienol	5364412	-4.4	-7.7
34	4.64	Kaempferol	5280863	-6.6	-10.7
35	3.90	Oleic Acid	445639	-4.5	-7.6
36	2.19	Cyclohexane, 2-propenyl-	75027	-5.0	-6.0
37	0.82	5-Eicosene, (E)-	5364600	-4.4	-7.3
38.	7.51	3-Eicosene, (E)-	5365051	-3.9	-7.2
39.	1.43	Ethanol, 2-(tetradecyloxy)-	16491	-4.2	-6.3
40.	4.13	Octadec-9-enoic acid	965	-4.5	-7.2
41	1.50	1-Dodecanol, 2-hexyl-	86112	-4.8	-6.8
42	3.35	2-Piperidinone, N-[4-bromo-n-butyl]-	536377	-5.1	-6.3
43	1.79	Cycloeicosane	520444	-5.6	-6.7
44	1.46	Cyclohexadecane, 1,2-diethyl-	536940	-6.7	-6.2
45	4.67	Catechin	9064	-6.6	-10.5
46.	1.11	Cyclotetracosane	520449	-7.3	-6.7

47.	0.65	Dodecane, 1,2-dibromo-	185803	-4.3	-6.4
48.	2.65	Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	8343	-5.5	-6.9
49	0.56	1-Octadecene	8217	-3.9	-6.8
50.	4.94	9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)-, 2-hydroxy-1-(hydroxymethyl)ethyl ester	5319879	-4.2	-7.2
51	0.67	Erucic acid	5281116	-4.1	-7.5
52	0.70	9-Octadecenal, (Z)-	5364492	-3.5	-6.9
53	2.22	2- Chloropropionic acid, hexadecyl	522865	-3.7	-7.0
54	2.58	Squalene	638072	-5.0	-8.1
55	0.84	cis-13-Octadecenoic acid	5312441	-4.6	-7.2
56	0.99	9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)-, 2,3-dihydroxypropyl ester	5283468	-4.6	-7.2
57	1.47	13-Octadecenal, (Z)-	5364497	-3.6	-7.0

(A) Omeprazole in 6gbg

(B) Kaempferol in 6gbg

(C) Catechin in 6gbg

(D) Omeprazole in 4inn

(E) Kaempferol 4inn

(F) Catechin 4inn

Figure 3(A-F). Visualized protein-ligand interactions between omeprazole, kaempferol, catechin and the two ulcer proteins.

3. 3. Absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion and toxicity (AMET) prediction Results

To function effectively as a drug, a compound must reach the target in the human body in rich concentration, and remain there in its bioactive form long enough for the expected biologic activity to take place. In drug discovery and evaluation, thorough assessment of absorption, distribution, metabolism excretion and toxicity (admet) are urgently needed to reduce failures in the drug discovery procedure. Admet predictions were achieved using admet SAR 2.0 on-line software available at <http://immd.ecust.edu.cn/admetSar2> [24].

This free online tool evaluates the pharmacokinetics, drug likeness, toxicity, and medicinal chemistry friendliness of small compounds. The admet prediction results which include human intestinal absorption (HIA), blood brain barrier (BBB), number of hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA), number of hydrogen bond donor (HBD), topological polar surface area (TPSA) are presented in Table 2. Interestingly, all three compounds obeyed the pizer's rule of five compiled by Lipinski [30]. The rule which helps to evaluate a compounds for its safety as an orally active drug states that for a compound to function as an orally active drug it should not violate more than one of the following: not have more than 5 hydrogen bond donors (HBD), not more than 10 hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA), the molecular mass should not be more than 500 daltons and the calculated octanol-water partition coefficient (ClogP) should not exceed 5.

The result shows that none of the compounds violated more than one of the Lipinski's rule implying that they would exert favorable impact when taken as drugs.

The three molecules studied showed positive human intestinal absorption indicating that they would be absorbed by the intestine. The presence of BBB protects the brain from damage by maintaining a stable environment [31], It plays a very important role in regulating the movement of necessary materials for brain function properly, also, protecting it from foreign materials in the blood that could destroy it [32]. The total polar surface area (TPSA) values were estimated and the parameter presented, the TPSA is used to predict the membrane permeability efficacy of a molecule, the range of value for this property is $20 \text{ \AA} < \text{TPSA} < 130 \text{ \AA}$ the obtained result showed that all three compounds fall within this range. Another important function estimated is the log P which refers to the logarithm of the partition coefficient.

The partition coefficient is a measure of the distribution of a drug between octanol and water phases. It indicates the lipophilicity or hydrophobicity of a drug, it is a function that is used to predict drug's ability to cross biological membranes, since most biological barriers are lipid-based. Its range of values for an ideal lead molecule in drug discovery is between 1 and 5. Drugs with a log P values greater than 5 are considered to be too lipophilic (non-polar), while those with values of log P less than 1 are said to be too hydrophilic (polar). Interestingly, our results for the three compounds are within this range showing that they would be good drug lead candidates for the management of ulcer disease.

Table 2. Admet Results.

S/No.	Compound	Molecular weight	HIA	BBB	ClogP	TPSA	HBA	HBD
1	Omeprazole	345.42	+	-	3.7654	96.31	5	1
2	Kaempferol	286.24	+	-	2.2824	111.13	6	4
3.	Catechin	290.27	+	-	1.5461	110.38	6	5

HIA = Human intestinal absorption, BBB = Blood brain, barrier, TPSA = Total polar surface area, ClogP = calculated octanol-water partition coefficient, HBA = Number of hydrogen bond acceptor, HBD = Number of hydrogen bond donor,

3. 4. Density Functional Theory Calculations

Density functional theory calculations were performed on the control drug, Kaempferol and catechin to investigate their reactivity towards the selected proteins. Calculations were performed using the electronic structure program DMol³ tools in the frame work of Mulliken population analysis, the DND basis set and the Perdew-Wang (PW) local correlation density functional [33, 34]. The frontier orbitals (HOMO) and (LUMO) as well as the optimized structures are presented in Figure 4. The quantum chemical parameters including absolute hardness (η), absolute electronegativity (χ), softness (δ) and electrophilicity (ω) [37] which were calculated from the HOMO and LUMO energies are tabulated in Table 3. Calculations were performed according the equations 1-4. The HOMO orbital is an electron rich center and

demonstrates the molecule's ability to donate electron while the LUMO orbital is an electron deficient center that shows the ability of a compound to accept electrons [36, 37]. The HOMO and LUMO orbitals are used to predict the most reactive regions in a compound. The energy gap between the HOMO and LUMO orbitals (ΔE) is used to describe the kinetic stability of a compound [38] high energy gap translates to high chemical stability whereas small HOMO-LUMO is translated to high reactivity. The ionization energy (I) is the energy required to remove the most loosely bound electron in the ground state on the molecule whereas the electron affinity (A) is the energy given off when an electron in its ground state gains an electron, high value of ionization energy shows chemical stability, but high electronic affinity values indicates that the compound would easily accept electrons. The electronegativity (χ) of a compound is a measure of its ability to attract electron. Electrophilicity (ω) is a property that is used to describes the electrophilic property of a compound; it shows the ability of a compound to attract electron to itself, high values of electrophilicity shows good electrophilicity in a molecule. Values of the quantum chemical properties obtained in Table 3 show that the studied compounds would exhibit good chemical reactivity.

Figure 4. Optimized structures, HOMO and LUMO orbitals of Omeprazole, Kaempferol and Catechin

Table 3. The calculated values of HOMO, LUMO energies and their corresponding quantum chemical parameters.

	Omeprazole	Kaempferol	Catechin
E_{HOMO} (eV)	-5.2412	-5.1270	-4.8316
E_{LUMO} (eV)	-1.9246	-2.6741	-0.7070
$I = -E_{\text{HOMO}}$ (eV)	5.2412	5.1270	4.8316
$A = -E_{\text{LUMO}}$ (eV)	1.9246	2.6741	0.7070
$\Delta E = E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}}$ (eV)	3.3166	2.4529	4.1246
χ (eV)	3.5829	3.9006	2.7693
η (eV)	1.6583	1.2265	2.0623
δ (eV) ⁻¹	0.6030	0.8153	0.4849
ω (eV)	3.8706	6.2025	1.8593

$$\eta = \frac{I-A}{2} \quad (1)$$

$$\chi = \frac{I+A}{2} \quad (2)$$

$$\delta = \frac{1}{\eta} \quad (3)$$

$$\omega = \frac{\chi^2}{2\eta} \quad (4)$$

4. CONCLUSIONS

The ulcer inhibiting properties of leaves extract from *Moringa olefera* was studied. GC-MS analysis was used to identify the chemical constituents of the plant. The GC-MS result revealed compounds with good therapeutic properties. The compounds were subjected to ulcer screening using molecular docking method. The docking results showed that Kaempferol and Catechin gave very good binding scores in the two ulcer proteins. Kaempferol (-6.6 kcal mol⁻¹, -10.7 kcal mol⁻¹) and Catechin (-6.6 kcal mol⁻¹, -10.5 kcal mol⁻¹) the results were even better than omeprazole which was used as the control drug (-6.6 kcal mol⁻¹, -9.1 kcal mol⁻¹), to ascertain the ability of the compounds to behave as consumable drugs, Absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion and toxicity (AMET) prediction was undertaken and the result showed that the compounds contained in *Moringa olefera* could function as good drugs for ulcer inhibition.

Density functional theory results predicted good reactivities between the compounds and the protein targets. The results obtained from the overall research showed that *Moringa oleifera* could comfortably inhibit ulcer sores without harm to human.

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